

THE ROLE OF CULTURE FOR SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN QUANG NGAI PROVINCE, VIETNAM

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Abstract:

Quang Ngai Province is in the process of renovation for sustainable development. The purpose and motivation of this development is culture. Thus, promoting the role of culture in international economic integration in Quang Ngai is now to link culture to life, conserve traditional values, and absorb world cultural values selectively.

Keywords: Quang Ngai province, culture, sustainable, role, motivation

1. Introduction

Globalization is becoming an indispensable trend in the modern world in many areas. On the perception of the world's context, the reality of the development of nations, it is possible to see the linkage of economic, security and political development which is not sustainable enough in each country or region if there is not enough orientation to build and develop culture and society. Because culture and society have close relationship with economy, security and politics, it can be seen that when the society is unfair, it threatens economic development, triggering security and political conflicts. When an economic crisis can directly threaten poverty, the risk of unemployment, disease and social evils. Social instability may be due to environmental depletion or uneven distribution. These social issues are imperative, which must be addressed to avoid causing economic and political turmoil.

2. Content

2.1. Vietnamese conception of the role of culture for sustainable economic development

Today, in the globalization and international integration, countries which want to develop sustainably must achieve harmony between economic growth and cultural construction. Culture includes all practical activities of human beings to form and

develop the society. In human society, the culture is created, developed, changed in accordance with history, geography. This creates the cultural characteristics of a community and a region. Human has created his second nature. It is culture. Ho Chi Minh stated (1999), "*There are four issues that must be paid attention to in the national construction, which are politic, economy, society and culture.*" Thus, harmonious development of economy and culture is the key to sustainable development. The economy is the basis, and the conditions for the formation, the development of culture. Taking that view into consideration, the Communist Party of Vietnam affirmed that economic development in harmony with cultural development, with social progress and equality, is the requirement of the socialist-oriented market economy. Culture is the spiritual foundation of society. It is both a goal and a driving force for economic and social development. The instruction for building the country in the transitional period to socialism has pointed out: to build an advanced culture imbued with national identity, to develop comprehensively, united in diversity, deeply imbued humanitarian, democratism, and progressive spirit; making culture coherent, permeating the whole of social life, becoming the important endogenous force of development. Thus, through the views of the Communist Party of Vietnam on the position and role of culture in the revolution, directly or indirectly, the role of cultural development in relation to the development of economy.

2.1.1 The role of economics in the dialectical relationship with culture

Economic development facilitates cultural development. According to Ho Chi Minh, economics is not independent of culture but has a dialectical relationship with each other, economics is also an area of culture. In 1943, Ho Chi Minh (1996) said that "*5 big points in building national culture are: building psychology, self-reliance and independence; moral construction, sacrifice yourself to benefit the masses; building society, all careers related to people's welfare in society; creating politics and civil rights; economic construction*". In a narrow sense, culture is a separating field in relation to other fields such as economy, politics, society and environment. In a broad sense, culture is anthropomorphisation of human activity, marking the surpassing of human to the natural state. In this way, all human activities are cultural activities including economic and political activities. Accordingly, culture in economic and social development is called soft power, supporting force and converging force. Practices increasingly show that culture cannot stand outside the development but must be in harmony with economic and political relations. Culture is not only a goal, a motivation but also the process of economic development and cultural development and promoting economic and social growth.

2.1.2 Culture is an activating force for economic development

Culture as a soft power, an endogenous strength, a spiritual foundation of a nation, plays a huge role in promoting the development of the economy in particular and the nation in general. The development of culture is the basis for sustainable and comprehensive economic development. If economics is the material foundation of

people and society, then culture is the spiritual foundation. Culture develops through the function of building human, fostering intellect, soul, morality, personality, lifestyle of individuals and communities, which will be an indispensable condition to promote economic stability.

2.1.3 Culture is the goal of economic and social development, the social moral foundation

In the view of the Communist Party of Vietnam, culture is the goal of economy. Economic development is to develop people. The Party Congress X stated: *"Make progress and social justice right in each step, each development policy; develop economy together with culture development, health, education etc; solve social issues for human development. Implementing the distribution system mainly according to labor results, economic efficiency, and the level of capital contribution and other resources, through social welfare"*. Thus, economic development must aim to build a rich, strong, democratic, fair, civilized society and people in that society are happy and develop comprehensively.

Culture is a spiritual foundation because culture has the function of shaping values, standards in the social life, controlling the behavior of each person, the whole society. Those values and norms are distilled, stored, developed in the historical process, becoming a system of typical values for a nation such as politics, morality, law, science and literature, arts, institutions, cultural institutions, customs, lifestyles ..., creating the essence, soul, cultural identity of each nation. Through economic and social developing objectives, economic development strategies and plans should be set up. All economic development plans must aim at the highest goal, ensuring the most basic requirements are protecting people, serving people, for the benefit of people, improving the quality of human life.

2.2. The reality of the role of culture in sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province, Vietnam

Culture is affirmed as the spiritual foundation of society, the driving force and goal of development. While we implement the plan to build an advanced culture, imbued with national identity, cultural products are operated in the market mechanism, both in terms of spiritual value and material value. Quang Ngai Province is a province located in the South Central coastal region of Vietnam, with 47 ethnic groups living together in this land. The authority and people of Quang Ngai are aware of the importance of cultural development in the cultural and social life, which has direct impact on the province's economic development, so there is a close coordination, active implement to the programs and plans of the province. In the process of development, the province's culture has had positive impacts as well as drawbacks to the socio-economic development.

2.2.1. The positive effects of culture on sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province today

The development of Quang Ngai culture contributes to building a spiritual foundation, creating a new cultural environment for the people in the province to develop the economy during the renovation period. The culture of Quang Ngai province now has a progressive development, meeting the spiritual foundation for the province's socio-economic development in the time of national reformation. The connection between culture and economy and between economy and culture was initially implemented. The spirit of initiative and creativity, social activeness of the people are promoted. Many traditional cultural values are unique to Quang Ngai province, some new features in ethical standards and cultural personality are gradually completed. Promoting love and affection for people, contributing to each other, helping each other in the process of creation, productive labor, and economic development are being conducted in Quang Ngai province.

Cultural environment has many positive and clear changes in patriotic emulation movements, revolutionary actions, contests of laws, history, national and human traditions. Arouse the tradition of revolutionary history, love of people. In 2017, the percentage of cultural families reached 85%, the proportion of people participating in cultural and sports activities compared to the province's population was 31.5%. The authorities at all levels are always interested in directing professional and public activities in the province so that the activities could take place excitingly.

Cultural preservation activities of Quang Ngai province not only protect the spiritual values of indigenous people but also promote the development of tourism services, promote the development of market economy in the period of innovation of the province. The process of immigration, exchange and contact the cultures between ethnic groups, which creates a diverse cultural identity. Cultural socialization activities have been promoted, many organizations and individuals care about and invest in cultural development. Cultural institutions have been strengthened, many cultural projects have been invested in renovation, restoration, construction, which better meets the province's cultural development; career in education and training, science and technology development, contributing to creating abundant human resources for socio-economic development.

Economic development creates material conditions for education and training to be developed. Many projects and programs of the governmental, provincial and local levels have invested in education effectively. The socialization of education has been promoted, society has become more and more interested in building relationships between schools, families and society. The scale of education and the network of education and training institutions have rapidly developed. Relatively complete education system from preschool to university. In 2017, there were 20 students who won prizes at the national selection exam, 100% of communes, wards and towns met the standard of education universalization. The work of educating ethnic students is paid attention, fully implemented the guidelines, priority policies and solutions to

improve the quality and quantity; vocational training is paid attention to, vocational training institutions are increasing in both quantity and quality, meeting the demand for vocational training among the people, contributing to creating a solid human resource of capacity and religion virtue for economic development during the province's renovation period.

The province's scientific and technological activities have got important achievements. In 2017, there are 42 topics and projects focusing on socio-economic development objectives, associated with new rural areas. Transferring a number of applications and projects into production has brought about certain efficiency. Promote businesses to protect brand assets, apply innovations and apply science and technology in production and business, participate in programs to improve productivity and product quality. Intellectual property activities focus on training and guidance on procedures for protection registration, construction consultancy, brand promotion, dissemination of legal documents to raise awareness of agencies and businesses, and people to develop a more sustainable economy.

The mass media system is developed and managed properly, meeting the people's understanding of socio-economic development in the renovation period. Currently, in Quang Ngai province, the mass media system has developed rapidly. In general, the local and central press agencies in the province have closely followed the events and problems arising in daily life to quickly, fully and promptly inform all happenings in the country, meeting the right and need of informing of the people. The province broadcasting system is widely developed, covering all areas of the province.

Quang Ngai Provincial Party Committee cares and implements cultural policy for religion, contributing to stabilizing political security in the province, and people are assured of socio-economic development. Following the Resolution of the Central Government and the Ordinance on Beliefs and Religions and the political system from the province to the grassroots, the province has focused on strengthening propaganda and dissemination of policies of the Party and State on belief and religion to religious people; take care of socio-economic development, help religious people to eradicate hunger and poverty, improve people's intellectual standards, build a cultural environment, live "good life, beautiful religion", "the gospel in the heart of society", strengthen the solidarity between people with religion and non-religion in the area. Every year, on the feasts of religion such as: Christian Christmas, Buddha's Birthday Celebration, etc. Quang Ngai provincial government visits the dignitaries of the religions. In general, the activities of religions in the province comply with the law. The majority of religious people follow well the guidelines, and policies of the Party and the law of the State. Community of religious people always upholds the spirit of national solidarity has a sense of local construction and actively supports movements, especially to help the poor and people with especially difficult circumstances, together develop the province's economy. The work of building and improving the quality of activities of cultural institutions has always been focused, especially to build and strengthen

grassroots cultural institutions, create favorable conditions for people of all classes to organize cultural activities.

2.2.2. The limitations of cultural role in sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province today

Although the progress made in the field of cultural development over the past time of Quang Ngai province has had a positive impact on the socio-economic development of the province during the renovation period, culture also has negative effects, not commensurate with economic development and cultural development and has not met the demand, which is the spiritual foundation to contribute to boosting the socio-economic development, the goal and the driving force to economy in the province.

Cultural development has not fully met the demand for high-quality human resources for cultural and also economic development. The quality of education and training in Quang Ngai province does not meet the requirements of socio-economic development, there is a big gap between the urban and remote areas. Higher education, professional education and vocational education in Quang Ngai province have not met the social needs, because they are not tied to the demand for the use of human resources of the province. Teaching and learning methods have not really promoted the activeness and creativity of students and students; teaching facilities are not enough. The necessary human resources such as agricultural engineers, machinery engineers, and civic engineers... are insufficient. High-quality human resources for technology and technical training do not come back the province to but stay and work in cities, which leads to the lack of high-quality human resource in the province.

Investment in human activities is lacking. For example, schools, where people are trained, serve directly for the process of socio-economic development, medical facilities for medical examination and treatment and people's health care, and social welfare projects etc. are invested only on quantity, so it has not really affected the lives of ethnic minorities. The education system, although invested heavily in capital, does not meet the demand of human resources in accordance with the province development, causing great waste in training costs and people. Culture and educational philosophy have not had fundamental innovations in reality.

The cultural development of Quang Ngai province during the renovation period still has many degrading values of culture and social morality, domestic violence, school violence, and religious beliefs among the people tends to increase; pragmatic, personal, self-centered tendencies, indifference, and indulgence are developing in society; Some political opportunists have taken advantage of spreading false, and reactionary views. The pollution of living environment, degradation of culture, security, social order, safety, food hygiene and safety, and traffic accidents are still serious. The cultural environment is polluted by social evils, and by the spread of superstitious, and toxic products and services. Poverty, deprivation, backwardness of cultural and spiritual life in many rural, mountainous, remote and ethnic minority areas has not been effectively overcome. The gap between cultural enjoyment among regions and

regions and social classes continues to expand. It is these limitations of the culture of Quang Ngai province that have affected the economic development in the province, and hindered the socio-economic development of the province.

3. Discussion

From the real conditions, the cause of cultural role for sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province is due to the fact that Quang Ngai is still a poor province overall, its socio-economic infrastructure is still low, the economy is mainly agricultural, depending on the weather and market prices. The development of its regions is not equal. A part of the population in remote areas and ethnic minority areas still faces many difficulties. Deforestation has seriously affected the ecological environment and cultural living conditions of the residents here. Climate has many unfavorable changes, epidemics for plants and animals occur continuously in many areas in the province. Although the orientation of cultural development and economic development of Quang Ngai has been planned, but the feasibility are not high, which makes the relationship of economy and culture separate.

The cultural role for sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province now requires a sharp leadership and direction, combining cultural development with human construction. The weaknesses and shortcomings are partly due to objective conditions, but they are mainly due to the shortcomings in leadership, direction and administration.

Thus, to promote the cultural role for sustainable economic development in Quang Ngai province in the future, it is necessary to combine harmonious development with cultural development and economic development, making fair progress in every step, in each development policy of the government; to strengthen education, raise awareness of committees, authorities and each party member on the role of the relationship between cultural and economic development; consider the combination of cultural and economic development as a force to accelerate the sustainable development process of Quang Ngai province in the renovation period; ensuring people's welfare, improving the quality of life, social justice, and comprehensive, balanced and sustainable development in terms of economy, culture and society.

Cultural development should be considered as a directing force for economic development, ensuring high-qualified human resources for the socio-economic sectors in the province. Put education in the most important place, innovate and improve people's intellectual, scientific and technological levels to modify the human resource for the economic and cultural development of Quang Ngai province. Paying attention to the comprehensive development of cultural and social fields in harmony with economic development and other sectors, fields, between urban and rural areas to create a comprehensive strength for economic and intellectual development, and to create gender equality, protect the rights of women and children.

4. Conclusion

Culture is a spiritual foundation because culture has the function of shaping values, standards in the social life, controlling the behavior of each person, and the whole society. Those values and norms are distilled, stored, developed in the historical process, becoming a system of typical values for a nation such as politics, morality, law, science and literature, arts, institutions, cultural institutions, customs, lifestyles etc. creating the essence, soul, cultural identity of each nation. Therefore, to develop economy sustainment in Quang Ngai province, it is necessary to raise the role of culture. Because culture is both a goal and a directing force for the construction of Socialism and national defense in Vietnam. Culture must directly contribute to building the country and people of Vietnam in the new era.

References

- The Communist Party of Vietnam (1998), *the 5th Conference Document, the Central Committee of the 8th Session*, National Political Publishing House, Hanoi.
- Communist Party of Vietnam (2006), *Documents of the 10th National Congress*, National Political Publishing House.
- Ho Chi Minh (1996), *Complete*, National Political Publishing House, Hanoi.
- Quang Ngai Provincial People's Committee (2017), *Report on socio-economic situation, national defense and security in 2017, development plan for 2018*.

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